

PERMANENT MISSION OF INDIA TO THE UNITED NATIONS NEW YORK

INDIA AND UNITED NATIONS

India's deepening engagement with the United Nations is based on its steadfast commitment to multilateralism and dialogue as the key for achieving shared goals and addressing common challenges faced by the global community including those related to peace building and peacekeeping, sustainable development, poverty eradication, environment, climate change, terrorism, disarmament, human rights, health and pandemics, migration, cyber security, space and frontier technologies like Artificial Intelligence, comprehensive reform of the United Nations, including the reform of the Security Council, among others.

Pic: Indian Delegates arrive for United Nations Security Conference San Francisco: L to R; seated - Sir V.T. Krishnamachari, Representative of Indian States; Sir Ramaswami Mudaliar, Head of Indian delegation, Supply member Viceroy's Executive Council and Sir Firoz Khan Noon, Defence member, Viceroy's Council, April 22, 1945. **Source:** UN Archives

India was among the select members of the United Nations that signed the Declaration by United Nations at Washington on 1 January 1942. India also participated in the historic UN Conference of International Organization at San Francisco from 25 April to 26 June 1945.

As a founding member of the United Nations, India strongly supports the purposes and principles of the UN and has made significant contributions to implementing the goals of the Charter, and the evolution of the UN's specialized programmes and agencies.

India strongly believes that the United Nations and the norms of international relations that it has fostered remain the most efficacious means for tackling today's global challenges. India is steadfast in its efforts to work with the committee of Nations in the spirit of multilateralism to achieve comprehensive and equitable solutions to all problems facing us including development and poverty eradication, climate change, terrorism, piracy, disarmament, peace building and peacekeeping, human rights.

HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE

Independent India viewed its membership at the United Nations as an important guarantee for maintaining international peace and security. India stood at the forefront during the UN's tumultuous years of struggle against colonialism and apartheid.

India was the co-sponsor of the landmark 1960 Declaration on UN on Granting of Independence to Colonial Countries and Peoples which proclaimed the need to unconditionally end colonialism in all its forms and manifestations. India was also elected the first chair of the Decolonization Committee (Committee of 24) where its ceaseless efforts to put an end to colonialism are well on record.

India was amongst the most outspoken critics of apartheid and racial discrimination in South Africa. In fact, India was the first country to raise this issue at the UN (in 1946) and played a leading role in the formation of a Sub-Committee against Apartheid set up by the General Assembly. When the Convention on Elimination of all forms of Racial Discrimination was adopted in 1965, India was among the earliest signatories.

India's status as a founding member of the Non-Aligned Movement and the Group of 77 cemented its position within the UN system as a leading advocate of the concerns and aspirations of developing countries and the creation of a more equitable international economic and political order.

Indians at United Nations

Mr. Arcot Ramasamy Mudaliar was India's delegate to the San Francisco Conference leading to the creation of the United Nations. He also had distinction of serving as the first President of the United Nations Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC) in 1946.

Mrs. Hansa Mehta represented India on the Nuclear Sub-Committee on the status of women in 1946. As the Indian delegate on the UN Human Rights Commission in 1947-48, she was responsible for changing the language of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights from "all men are created equal" to "all human beings", highlighting the need for gender equality.

Mrs. Lakshmi Menon, India's delegate to the Third Committee in 1948, argued forcefully in favour of non-discrimination based on sex and "the equal rights of men and women" in the in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. A strong advocate of the "universality" of human rights, she argued that "if women and people under colonial rule were not explicitly mentioned in the Universal Declaration, they would not be considered included in "everyone".

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Mrs. Vijaya Lakshmi Pandit had the distinction of being the first woman to be elected President of the United Nations General Assembly in 1953.

Mr. Chinmaya Rajaninath Gharekhan

served as ECOSOC President in 1990. In January 1993 was appointed by the UN Secretary General as a special envoy to the Middle East peace process in the capacity of Under-Secretary-General of the United Nations, a position he held until 1999.

1947 - 1956 P. S. Lokanathan
(India) Executive Secretary,
UNESCAP

1956-1967: Binay Ranjan Sen
Director General of the FAO

1965-1967: Manohar Balaji
Sarwate, Secretary-General,
ITU

1956 - 1959 Chakravarthi V.
Narasimhan, Executive
Secretary of UNESCAP

1968: Sushil K. Dev (India)
Acting Executive Director, World
Food Programme

1978-1992: Arcot
Ramachandran, Executive
Director of UN- Habitat

1974-1989: Chandrika Prasad
Srivastava, Secretary-General
of the International Maritime
Organization (IMO)

1979-1981: Padinjarethalakal
Cherian Alexander, Executive
Director, Int'l Trade Centre

1985 - 1988: Judge Nagendra
Singh, President of the
International Court of Justice

2009 - 2012: Judge Kamaljit Singh Garewal, Judge on the UN Appeals Tribunal (UNAT)

Currently there are **seven Indians in senior leadership positions** at the United Nations at the levels of Under Secretary General and Assistant Secretary General.

Mr. Atul Khare,
Under-Secretary-General, Dpt.
of Operational Support

Ms. Anita Bhatia,
Assistant Secretary-General &
Deputy Executive Director of the
UN Women

**Mr. Chandramouli
Ramanathan,** Assistant
Secretary-General, Dept of Mgt
Strategy, Policy & Compliance

Mr. Nikhil Seth,
ASG & Executive Director,
UNITAR

Mr. Satya S. Tripathi,
ASG, UNEP

Lt General Shailesh Tinaikar,
Force Commander, UNMISS

Judge Dalveer Bhandari,
Judge, ICJ

Mr. Ovais Sarmad, ASG &
Deputy Executive Secretary,
UNFCC

UN COMMITTEES

First Committee: Disarmament & International Security

The First Committee deals with disarmament, global challenges and threats to peace that affect the international community and seeks out solutions to the challenges in the international security regime. The Committee works in close cooperation with the United Nations Disarmament Commission and the Geneva-based Conference on Disarmament.

India is committed to non-proliferation in all its aspects. Accordingly, India has joined various multilateral export control regimes. With a view to address global concerns on the proliferation of WMD to terrorists, India has been tabling the consensus resolution on 'Measures to Prevent Terrorists from Acquiring WMD'. With a view to promote effective

Pic: India's Defence Minister V.K. Krishna Menon addresses a First Committee meeting to consider the priority to be given to the items on its agenda. (17 October 1961)

implementation of UNSCR 1540, India, in cooperation with Germany and the UNODA, hosted the India-Wiesbaden Conference 2018 in April 2018.

India remains committed to the goal of a nuclear weapon free world and complete elimination of nuclear weapons. It believes that this goal can be achieved through a step-by-step process underwritten by a universal commitment and an agreed global and non-discriminatory multilateral framework, as outlined in India's Working Paper on Nuclear Disarmament submitted to the UNGA in 2006.

India attaches great importance to the Chemical Weapons Convention (CWC) which embodies the global norm against the use of chemical weapons. It has been India's consistent position that the use of chemical weapons anywhere, at any time, by anybody, under any circumstances, cannot be justified and the perpetrators of such acts must be held accountable. At a time when the Convention is facing serious challenges, India is committed to maintaining its credibility and integrity.

India remains opposed to the weaponization of outer space. India has not, and will not, resort to any arms race in outer space. India has been a consistent advocate of preserving the outer space as a common heritage of humankind, as an ever-expanding frontier for cooperative endeavors of all space faring nations.

India supports substantive consideration of the prevention of an arms race in outer space within the multilateral framework of the UN. India is committed to negotiation of a legally-binding instrument on the prevention of an arms race in outer space to be negotiated in the Conference on Disarmament, where it has been on the agenda since 1982. India has been an active participant in the Group of Governmental Experts on the Prevention of an Arms Race in Outer Space which concluded its session in March 2019. India also participated in deliberation on TCBMs held in informal meeting of the UNDC April 2019.

At the 73rd session of the First Committee in 2018, India voted in favor of all resolutions submitted under the Outer Space cluster, including on the Prevention of an arms race in outer space (which India also co-sponsored), on further practical measures for the prevention of an arms race in outer space, on No first placement of weapons in outer space as well as on Transparency and confidence-building measures in outer space activities.

The Role of Science and Technology in the context of International Security and Disarmament: This issue was first added to the agenda of the First Committee in 1988, with India as the main sponsor. In introducing a draft resolution, the Indian delegate recalled that increasing amounts of resources were being devoted to developing new weapon systems, which caused uncertainty and insecurity. Developments such as the graduated use of nuclear explosive power, miniaturization and large-scale computing capabilities using micro-electronics, and fuel and laser technology were transforming the security environment. Therefore, it was argued that work should be initiated to develop a shared perception of the problems involved and to make possible concerted efforts to

resolve them. On 7 December 1988, the first resolution on the issue, 43/77 A was adopted with a recorded vote of 129 in favour, 7 against with 14 abstentions.

Since 2017, India has been presenting resolution on the 'role of science and technology in the context of international security and disarmament' which has been adopted by consensus and attracted co-sponsors across regions. The resolution had mandated the UNSG to submit a report on the current developments in science and technology and their potential impact on international security and disarmament efforts.

India remains committed to playing a leading and constructive role together with other partners, in deliberations and negotiations on prevention of an arms race in outer space, including legally binding measures, TCBMs and long-term sustainability guidelines.

Second Committee: Economic & Financial

The Second Committee deals with issues relating to economic growth and development such as macroeconomic policy questions; financing for development; sustainable development; human settlements; globalization and interdependence; eradication of poverty; operational activities for development; agriculture development, food security and nutrition; information and communications technologies for development; and towards global partnerships.

Pic: Mr. I.S. Chadha of India (first from right) at the Second Committee meeting on the World Economic Situation

India presented its 'Voluntary National Review Report on Implementation of Sustainable Development Goals' at the United Nations high-level political forum on sustainable development in 2017. It highlighted that apart from integrating the SDGs into its on-going national and sub-national policies and programmes, India will continue to focus on nurturing partnerships at the regional and global levels.

In 2020, the 50 countries (27 first time presenters, and 23 second time presenters) will be conducting Voluntary National Reviews at the HLPF. India will be among the countries that will be presenting its VNR for the second time (first time presented in 2017). The VNR presentations are planned to begin on Monday, 13 July 2020 (the last of the first five days of HLPF) and proceed for the three days of the ministerial segment of HLPF (14 – 16 July 2020).

India has consistently reiterated its support to multilateral trading system and the centrality of the WTO as the cornerstone of a rule based, open, transparent, non-discriminatory and inclusive multilateral trading system with development at the core of its agenda. India has underlined that the reform of institutions such as the IMF remains an important goal to better address the interests of the developing nations.

India actively contributed to the debates and deliberations leading to the adoption of the Global Compact on Safe, Orderly and Regular Migration. India believes that safe, orderly and regular Migration will help in achievement of SDGs and achievement of SDGs will ensure that Migration will be out of choice and not out of compulsion.

Third Committee: Social, Humanitarian & Cultural

The Third Committee deals with a range of social, humanitarian affairs and human rights issues that affect people all over the world. The Committee discusses questions relating to the advancement of women, the protection of children, indigenous issues, the treatment of refugees, the promotion of fundamental freedoms through the elimination of racism and racial discrimination, and the right to self-determination. It also addresses important social development questions such

Pic: India's Permanent Representative Samar Sen attends Third Committee Meeting on East Pakistan Refugees, 1971

as issues related to youth, family, ageing, persons with disabilities, crime prevention, criminal justice, and international drug control.

Representing India at the first session of the Commission of Human Rights in 1947, drafting the Universal Declaration of the Human Rights, Dr. Hansa Mehta, a bold and visionary woman social activist, played an important role in ensuring that the first Article of the UDHR spoke of 'all human beings' rather than 'all men' being 'free and equal'. This was well before equal rights for women and men were recognized in most legal systems.

India has consistently underlined that genuine improvement in human rights cannot be achieved by undertaking aggressive and overly intrusive methods without consultation and consent of the country concerned. Such confrontational approach is counterproductive, leading to politicization of human rights issues. India believes that only an approach based on dialogue, consultation and cooperation with non-selectivity and transparency as guiding principles will be effective.

India has partnered UN Women since its inception to address critical issues concerning gender equality and empowerment of women in national and global context. India has so far made voluntary contribution of US\$ 8 million to UN Women for its global operations. It is in this context that India facilitated the field visit of the UN-Women Executive Board Bureau to India in 2017 which provided an opportunity for the UN Women delegation to gain first-hand understanding of UN-Women's work at the country level and its cooperation with the Government of India.

Fourth Committee: Special Political & Decolonization

Pic: India Chairs the Special Committee on Decolonization - 1962

The Fourth Committee considers a broad range of issues related to decolonization, the effects of atomic radiation, questions relating to information, a comprehensive review of the question of peacekeeping operations as well as a review of special political missions, the United Nations Relief and Works Agency for

Palestinian Refugees in the Near East (UNRWA), the Report of the Special Committee on Israeli Practices and International cooperation in the peaceful uses of outer space. In addition to these annual items, it also considers the items on assistance in mine action, and University for peace biennially and triennially respectively.

As a country that itself was colonized, India has always been in the forefront of the struggle against colonialism and apartheid since its own independence seven decades ago. India was actively engaged with the organization of the historic Afro-Asian Conference at Bandung, Indonesia in 1955. Five years later, India was the co-sponsor of the landmark 1960 Declaration on the Granting of Independence to Colonial Countries and Peoples, which was adopted by the General Assembly. The Declaration proclaimed the need to unconditionally end colonialism in all its forms and manifestations.

India believes that pursuing a pragmatic approach towards Decolonization would lead to fulfillment of legitimate wishes of the people of 17 Non-Self-Governing Territories. India has consistently called for increased efforts to reach the conclusion of this long-drawn process.

India is in favour of integrated studies of radiobiology and epidemiology at international level in order to collect more systematic information about health effects of low dose of radiation and re-examine (linear no-threshold model) LNT hypothesis.

India has supported efforts to build mutual trust and confidence, including through the discussions on Long Term Sustainability of Outer Space activities at UNCOPUOS. India has also supported substantive consideration of the issue of Prevention of Arms Race (PAROS) at the Conference on Disarmament. India has also been actively engaged in capacity building in space law, through hosting several national and international workshops and seminars on these issues.

In 2017, India hosted the 24th session of the Asia Pacific Regional Space Agency Forum (APRSAF) with the theme 'Space Technology for Enhanced Governance and Development' in Bengaluru. The same year India hosted the 38th Asian Conference of Remote Sensing with the theme 'Space Applications: Touching Human Lives' in New Delhi. In June 2018 India hosted the 46th Plenary of the Coordination Group on Meteorological Satellites (CGMS). The Indian Space Research Organisation (ISRO) continues to share its facilities and expertise through the UN-affiliated Centre for Space Science and Technology Education in Asia and the Pacific (CSSTEAP) based in Dehradun. There have been more than 1600 participants from more than 50 countries.

Fifth Committee: Administrative & Budgetary

The Fifth Committee considers and approves the budget of the United Nations. It also considers and approves financial and budgetary arrangements with specialized agencies and makes recommendations to the agencies concerned. It may also consider urgent matters relating to the financing of a peacekeeping mission authorized by the Security Council at any of its sessions.

India has stressed that resource allocation should be commensurate with our collective commitment towards realization of the Agenda 2030. The UN system must be adequately resourced to service the Member States in achieving this goal. The imperative of 'doing more with less', rationalization of resources should not undermine the ability of the UN

system to deliver its mandate. India has supported delegation of authority to managers at the field level, aligning authority with responsibility and changing organizational designs to strengthen accountability.

India's share of the UN's budget has been increasing in recent years, including a 13% increase from 2019 in its assessment rates. India is one of the few countries which has been paying all assessments in full and on time, including peacekeeping contributions.

Pic: Maharaja Jam Sahab of Nawanagar of India (second from left), Chairs the Fifth Committee of the UN, 1950

India is among those member states who continue to be owed significant sums towards troop and COE reimbursements from the active peacekeeping missions. India has highlighted that these arrears and recurrent delay in reimbursement have turned the Troop Contributing Countries (TCCs) as de facto financiers of UN peacekeeping, which is involuntary and beyond many TCCs' capacity to pay. As per latest figures, as of 30 September 2020, \$357 million was owed to Member States for troops and formed police units, compared to \$6 million last year.

The ongoing liquidity crisis in the regular budget is a cause for concern. While the cash position has improved slightly as compared to the previous years, it can be attributed primarily to austerity measures such as the hiring freeze, and lower spending due to COVID-19. This calls for our continued focus on the issue.

The fallout of the COVID-19 pandemic continues to be a challenge in the 75th session of the General Assembly and for the working of the Fifth Committee. However, India remains fully committed to a thorough consideration of the agenda items allocated to the Committee and in the weeks ahead will address issues of crucial importance to the General Assembly and the Organization. The Group will actively engage in the deliberations of this session on both the Proposed Programme Plan and Programme Budget for 2021.

Moreover, India also intends to actively participate in the Committee's deliberations on other agenda items, including the review of the implementation of the peace and security pillar reform, review of the implementation of resolution 72/266B, Construction and Property Management, the funding model of the DMSPC and DOS, Review of budgetary

cycle involving CPC and ACABQ Sequencing, the United Nations Common System, Pension System, Umoja and Administration of Justice. Close attention will also be paid to deliberations on the Scale of Assessments, the Capital Master Plan, all programme budget implications and revised estimates, Improving the Financial Situation of the United Nations, as well as the reports of the Board of Auditors and the OIOS.

Sixth Committee: Legal

Pic: On left, Sixth Committee expert Mr. Akbar Ali Khan (India), 1953

The Sixth Committee is the primary forum for the consideration of legal questions in the General Assembly.

India is an active participant in the multilateral efforts at developing collective management of ocean affairs and one of the early parties to the 1982 UN Convention on the Law of the Sea. In addition to UNCLOS, India is a party to the Agreement relating to the implementation of Part XI of the Convention of 10 December 1982, Fish

Stocks Convention 1995, MARPOL 73/78, the International Ballast Water Convention 2004 that protects invasive aquatic Alien species, the London Convention 1972 and other agreements that regulate various activities of the oceans, especially the conservation and sustainable use of ocean resources.

India is actively engaged in discussions and negotiations towards developing norms relating to the emerging complex areas of Marine Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction (BBNJ) and Global Geospatial Information Management (GGIM).

India played an active role in the first Cycle of the Regular Process during 2010-2015, which resulted in the First Global Integrated Marine Assessment on the state of the health of the oceans. India is also playing an active role in the second cycle of the Regular Process (2017 – 2020) for preparation of a second world ocean assessment and Regular Process support to other ongoing ocean-related processes. India contributed its expertise in the area of marine chemistry, physical oceanography, marine geology, and marine biology.

India continues to make serious efforts to bring its national laws in consonance with its international obligations. India is a party to the Paris Agreement on Climate Change

under UNFCCC, and Doha Amendment to the Kyoto Protocol. India has acceded to the UN Customs Convention on International Transport Goods under cover of TIR carnets and also signed the UN (Singapore) Convention on International Settlement Agreements Resulting from Mediation. In the last few years, India has enacted nearly 43 new acts, ranging from legislations on Mental Health, Rights of persons with disabilities, Civil Aviation, labour and employment, agriculture and farmers' welfare, Goods and Services Tax, National Waterways, Anti-Hijacking etc.

India is a member of the United Nations Commission on International Trade Laws (UNCITRAL) since its establishment and also playing an active role in its all six working groups. India is a party to UNCITRAL Model Law on International Commercial Arbitration and the New York Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards (New York Convention) — provide the bases upon which contracting states may adopt domestic laws to implement a cross-border arbitration system and has adopted, in large measure, the UNCITRAL Model Law through the Indian Arbitration and Conciliation Act of 1996 (the Arbitration Act).

India has been contributing to the Residual Special Court for Sierra Leone to enable the Court to carry out its functions effectively.

Indian Contribution to United Nations Peacekeeping

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India has a long and distinguished history of service in UN peacekeeping, having contributed more personnel than any other country. To date, more than 253000 Indians have served in 49 of the 71 UN peacekeeping missions established around the world since 1948. Currently, there are around 5,500 troops & police from India who have been deployed to UN peacekeeping missions, the fifth highest amongst troop-contributing countries.

Commencing with its participation in the UN operation in Korea in 1950s, India's mediatory role in resolving the stalemate over prisoners of war in Korea led to the signing of the armistice ending the Korean War. India chaired the five-member Neutral Nations Repatriation Commission while the Indian Custodian Force supervised the process of interviews and repatriation that followed. The UN entrusted Indian armed forces with subsequent peace missions in the Middle East, Cyprus, and the Congo (since 1971, Zaire). India also served as chair of the three international commissions for supervision and control for Vietnam, Cambodia, and Laos established by the 1954 Geneva Accords on Indochina.

India has a long tradition of sending women on UN peacekeeping missions. In 2007, India became the first country to deploy an all-women contingent to a UN peacekeeping mission. The Formed Police Unit in Liberia provided 24-hour guard duty and conducted night patrols in the capital Monrovia and helped to build the capacity of the Liberian police. Hailed as role models, these female officers not only played a vital role in restoring

security in the West African nation but also contributed to an increase in the number of women in the Liberia's security sector. In addition to their security role, the members of the female Indian Formed Police Unit also distinguished themselves through humanitarian service, including organizing medical camps for Liberians, many of whom have limited access to health care services.

Medical care is among the many services Indian peacekeepers provide to the

Indian troops join Danish and Swedish peacekeepers on a training exercise on a beach in Gaza in 1958 as part of the UN Emergency Force (UNEF).

communities in which they serve on behalf of the Organization. They also perform specialized tasks such as veterinary support and engineering services. Indian veterinarians serving with the UN Mission in South Sudan (UNMISS), stepped up to help cattle herders who were losing much of their stock to malnutrition and disease in the war-torn nation. The Indian contingent in South Sudan has gone the extra mile by providing vocational training and life-saving medical assistance, as well as carrying out significant road repair work.

The Indian contingent in the Upper Nile region (includes the Indian Battalion, the Horizontal Mechanical Engineering Company, the Level II hospital, the Petroleum Platoon and the Force Signal Unit) have all received UN medals of honour for their dedication and service in peacekeeping.

Indian peacekeepers have also brought the ancient Indian practice of yoga to UN missions. Members of the UN mission in Lebanon, UNIFIL and UNMISS, South Sudan celebrate the International Yoga Day.

India has provided 17 Force Commanders to various missions. Besides the Force Commanders, India also had the honour of providing two Military Advisors, one Female Police Adviser and one Deputy Military Advisor to the Secretary General of the United Nations. India was the first country to contribute to the Trust Fund on sexual exploitation and abuse, which was set up in 2016. India's longstanding service has not come without cost. 173 Indian peacekeepers have paid the ultimate price while serving with the United Nations. India has lost more peacekeepers than any other Member State.

In September 2020, based on an urgent request received from the UN Secretariat, India deployed two medical teams of 15 medical personnel each at Goma (DRC) and Juba (South Sudan). The main hub of command-and-control center of MONUSCO is located in Goma, DRC. The Hospital by India in Goma, operational since January 2005, has 90 Indian nationals including 18 specialists. Given the rising COVID cases in the area, the "Level-3" facility, which is the highest level of medical care provided by a deployed UN unit, is now being upgraded to a Level-3 Plus facility. The "Level-2 plus" Hospital by India in Juba, South Sudan (UNMISS), operational since December 2016, has 77 Indian nationals including 12 specialists. The Indian facility in Juba is presently the one of highest level of medical facilities existing in South Sudan. This facility is now being upgraded from Level-2 plus to a Level-3 facility.

75TH ANNIVERSARY OF THE UN

The year 2020 marks the **75th anniversary** of the United Nations and its founding Charter. This anniversary comes in a time of great disruption for the world, compounded by an unprecedented global health crisis due to the COVID-19 pandemic, with severe economic and social impacts. Many of the **planned modalities of the commemoration**, agreed to by Member States in 2019, have had to be modified in view of the restrictions on international travel and in-person meetings, leading to **virtual and hybrid-format events**.

The UN marked the occasion with a **High-Level Meeting of the 75th UN General Assembly** on 21 September 2020 on the theme '*The Future We Want, the UN We Need: Reaffirming our Collective Commitment to Multilateralism*'. In his intervention, Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi highlighted the need for a **reformed multilateralism** that reflects today's realities, gives voice to all stakeholders, addresses contemporary challenges and focuses on human welfare. During this meeting, world leaders also adopted the **UN@75 Political Declaration** commemorating 75 years of the UN.

Other commemorative events included observance ceremonies to mark the 75th anniversary of the signing of the **UN Charter** (26 June 2020) and to mark the **75th UN Day** (24 October 2020). A special **UN@75 Virtual Youth Plenary** was also organised on 9 September 2020.

The **75th session of the UN General Assembly** opened on 15 September 2020, with Ambassador Volkan Bozkir of Turkey as President (PGA). Upon taking office, the new PGA emphasized that in his term, his **priority areas** will be:

- i. Fighting COVID-19 together
- ii. Celebrating 75 years of the UN
- iii. Recommitting to and strengthening Multilateralism
- iv. Advancing humanitarian agenda with a focus on the most vulnerable
- v. Taking action to achieve the 2030 Agenda and SDGs
- vi. Promoting Gender Equality

The theme for the **75th UNGA General Debate** was *“The future we want, the United Nations we need: reaffirming our collective commitment to multilateralism – confronting COVID-19 through effective multilateral action”*. Addressing the General Assembly (through per-recorded message) in the General Debate on 26 September 2020, **Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi** said called for **urgent reform of the United Nations** and for inclusion of **India’s voice** in its decision-making structures. He also outlined **India’s contribution to the global response to the COVID-19 pandemic**, announcing that India will make available its vaccine production and delivery capacities to the rest of the world, in keeping with its philosophy of seeing the **world as one family**.

Other UN@75 initiatives: In January 2020, the United Nations also launched a **“global conversation”** to mark its 75th anniversary. Through **ongoing surveys and informal dialogues** with multiple stakeholders including civil society, youth and women, this initiative seeks to **understand peoples’ expectations** of international cooperation and of the UN in particular. It is also the largest survey to date on priorities for recovering from the COVID-19 pandemic. Early results from the survey indicate that amid the COVID-19 pandemic, the immediate priority of most respondents is improved access to basic services, and increased support for tackling poverty, inequalities and boosting employment.

Representation in UN Bodies

India has continued its successful run at the elections to various UN bodies. India has won several major elections in the last few years including elections to the Human Right Council (HRC), Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC), Ms. Jagjit Pavadia’s election to International Narcotics Control Board (INCB), Judge Dalveer Bhandari’s election to International Court of Justice (ICJ), Amb Preeti Saran’s election to Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (CESCR), Dr. Neeru Chadha’s election to International Tribunal for the Law of the Sea (ITLOS), Dr. Aniruddha Rajput’s election to International Law Commission (ILC), Amb. P. Gopinathan’s election to Joint Inspection Unit (JIU), among others.

Currently India is represented in the following 23 UN Bodies whose elections are held at United Nations headquarters in New York.

1.	United Nations Commission on International Trade Law (UNCITRAL)	2016-2022
2.	International Seabed Authority (ISA) Council	2017-2020

3.	Legal and Technical Commission of the ISA	2017-2021
4.	Finance Committee of ISA	2017-2021
5.	International Law Commission (ILC) - Dr. Aniruddha Rajput	2017-2021
6.	Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC)	2018-2020
7.	International Court of Justice (ICJ) - Judge Dalveer Bhandari	2018-2026
8.	Joint Inspection Unit (JIU) - Amb. P. Gopinathan	2018-2022
9.	Commission on Population and Development (CPD)	2018-2021
10.	Commission for Social Development (CSocD)	2018-2021
11.	Commission on Narcotic Drugs (CND)	2018-2021
12.	Human Rights Council (HRC)	2019-2021
13.	Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (CESCR) - Ambassador Preeti Saran	2019-2022
14.	Committee on Non-Governmental Organizations (CNGO)	2019-2022
15.	Executive Board of UNDP/UNFPA/UNOPS	2019-2021
16.	Executive Board of UN-Women	2019-2021
17.	Commission on Crime Prevention and Criminal Justice (CCPCJ)	2019-2021
18.	Programme Coordination Committee of UN AIDS Executive Board	2020-2022
19.	International Narcotics Control Board (INCB) - Ms. Jagjit Pavadia	2020-2025
20.	Committee for Programme and Coordination (CPC)	2021-23
21.	Commission on the Status of Women	2021-25
22.	Commission on Population and Development	2021-25
23.	Advisory Committee on Administrative and Budgetary Questions – Ms. Vidisha Maitra	2021-23

Familiarization visits to India

India has been closely engaging with the global community at the United Nations by promoting familiarization visits to India by the Ambassadors/Permanent Representatives of various member states represented at the United Nations. In the last two years, UN Ambassadors of over 50 countries have undertaken visits to India for a better understanding of India's growth dynamics, vibrant democracy, developments in science and technology, including atomic energy and space science. The next visit for UN Ambassadors is being planned for 2021/2022, depending on the COVID-19 situation.

Significant Achievements

2014-20

1. Major Initiatives:

- The UNGA Resolution declaring 21 June every year as the International Day of Yoga was adopted in Dec 2014 with a record number of 177 co-sponsors. This set-in motion global annual observance of the International Day of Yoga.

- Usage of Hindi in UN public communications (UN news, weekly audio bulletins on UN radio and UN social media) began in March 2018 following the first MoU signed by the UN with any country.
- The first evert single-country South-South cooperation initiative at the UN was launched in June 2017 through the “India-UN Development Partnership Fund”, a \$100 million fund facility to undertake projects across the developing world. In April 2018, a US\$50 Million Commonwealth window was created under the Fund to support SDG related projects in developing countries of the Commonwealth.
- Following the efforts made in three previous attempts (2009, 2016 and 2017), the Security Council finally on 1 May 2019 approved the addition of Masood Azhar to the 1267 Sanctions of individuals and entities subject to the assets freeze, travel ban and arms embargo.

2. Elections: India is one of the few countries whose candidates have won every election at the UN in New York.

- The election of Judge Dalveer Bhandari to the International Court of Justice (ICJ) in Nov 2017 was a landmark event for India in terms of its unprecedented success in unseating a sitting judge from UK, a P5 member.
- Dr. Neeru Chadha became the first Indian woman to be elected in June 2017 as Judge of the International Tribunal for the Law of the Sea (ITLOS) for the period 2017-2026.
- Dr. Aniruddha Rajput was elected to the International Law Commission (ILC) in Nov 2016 for the term 2017-2021 with highest number of votes (Total of 160 out of 193 votes) in the Asia-Pacific Group.
- India was elected to the Human Rights Council in Oct 2018 for the period 2019-2022 with highest number of votes (188/193).
- Ms. Jagjit Pavadia was re-elected as Member to the International Narcotics Control Board (INCB) on 7th May 2019 for the term 2020-25 with the highest number of votes (44 out of the 54-member ECOSOC).
- On 15 Sept 2020, India was elected to the Commission of the Status of Women by the ECOSOC. India secured 38 out 54 votes polled. India’s tenure on the CSW will last from 2021 to 2025. India was also elected to the Committee for Programme and Coordination (CPC) and Commission on Population and Development.
- Ms. Vidisha Maitra was elected to the Advisory Committee on Administrative and Budgetary Questions by vote of the General Assembly. Ms. Vidisha won the highest number of votes - 126 out of the 192 valid votes (with 2 abstentions).

3. Other achievements / participation in important events:

- In Nov 2017, a voluntary compact was reached between UN Secretary-General and the Government of India on commitment to eliminate sexual exploitation and abuse in peacekeeping, humanitarian and development work. Prime Minister also joined the Circle of Leadership on the prevention of and response to sexual exploitation and abuse in United Nations operations
- In Sept 2018, UNEP recognized Prime Minister Modi in the “Policy Leadership” category for pioneering work in championing the International Solar Alliance and

for the pledge to eliminate single-use plastic in India by 2022. UNEP also selected Cochin International Airport, which is fully-powered by solar energy, for the Champion for entrepreneurial vision award.

- International Solar Alliance (ISA) was registered with the UN as a treaty-based inter-governmental organization with effect from 9th Feb 2018.
- India ratified the Paris Agreement and 'Second commitment period of Kyoto Protocol' in Climate Change in Aug 2017.
- UNGA adopted a Resolution in Dec 2014 on recognizing the Indian festivals of Diwali, Buddha Purnima and GURPURAB by the UN. The first official celebration of Diwali at UN Headquarters took place in 2016.
- First reference to 'Yoga' was made in Sept 2018 in the Political Declaration on Non-Communicable Diseases, a health-related resolution in UNGA.
- India was among the 40 plus countries in 2017 that presented their Voluntary National Review at the UN on the progress made in achievement of SDGs. India presented its second VNR virtually at the 2020 HLPF on 13 July 2020. Vice Chairman of NITI Aayog Mr Rajiv Kumar presented India's VNR. India's commitment to the SDGs was presented by highlighting our national development agenda as reflected in the motto of Sabka Saath Sabka Vikaas (Collective Efforts for Inclusive Growth).
- In Nov 2018, India successfully operationalized the co-deployment of 120 troops from Kazakhstan as part of its contingent in UN Interim Force in Lebanon (UNIFIL). India also initiated the process of deployment of a mixed Formed Police Unit to UN Mission in South Sudan.
- India's contribution to the Voluntary Trust Fund of the UN Tax Committee (to promote the participation of developing countries in the work of UN committee on tax matters that looks at key issues that could mobilize resources for sustainable development) was recognized in UNGA Resolution of Sept 2017.
- UN Day Concert (featuring Sarod Maestro Ustad Amjad Ali Khan) organized on 24 Oct 2018 after a gap of 52 years under the theme, "Traditions of Peace and Non-Violence".
- On 24th September 2019, India commemorated the 150th birth anniversary of Mahatma Gandhi by holding a high-level event at the UN. The event was hosted by Prime Minister Modi in which the UNSG Antonio Guterres, President of South Korea Moon Jae In, Prime Minister of Bangladesh Sheikh Hasina, Prime Minister of New Zealand Jessica Arden, and Prime Minister of Jamaica Andrew Holness.
- United Nations Postal Administration (UNPA) brought out the following three postal stamps in collaboration with the Mission: (i) Personalized stamp sheet on Birth Centenary and 50th Anniversary of Performance at the UN by M.S. Subbulakshmi; (ii) Special commemorative stamp sheet on International Day of Yoga; (iii) Special commemorative stamp sheet on Diwali; and (iv) Special commemorative stamp on the 150th birth anniversary of Mahatma Gandhi.
- Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi delivered a virtual keynote address at the High-Level Segment of the ECOSOC on 17 July 2020. The theme of the session was "Multilateralism after COVID 19: What kind of UN do we need at the 75th anniversary?" PM in his remarks touched upon several subjects such as India's commitment to achieve the SDGs and actions taken to combat COVID-19

pandemic. PM pitched for reformed multilateralism and human-centric globalization.

- Prime Minister Modi delivered his virtual address at the UN on 21st Sept 2020 on the occasion of the 75th anniversary of the founding of the UN. He also delivered India's national statement at the 75th UNGA General Debate on 26th Sept 2020. In his General Debate speech, PM said "A fragmented world is in the interest of no one", he said. "In this new era, we will have to give new direction to multilateralism, and to the United Nations".
- Prime Minister Narendra Modi spoke virtually at the Climate Ambition Summit on 12 Dec 2020. He pledged that by 2047, centennial India will exceed the world's expectations in implementing actions to counter climate change. He said, "on the occasion of the fifth anniversary of the Paris Agreement the world shouldn't lose sight of historical emissions". He called for a review of actions taken by all countries based on the commitments they had made under the agreement.

India's Priorities for the 77th session of the United Nations General Assembly

A. Introduction

1. The 77th session of the United Nations General Assembly [77th UNGA] will open on 13 September 2022 and will end on 12 September 2023. The General Debate of the 77th UNGA will be held from 20-26 September 2022. The theme of the General Debate will be "*A watershed moment: transformative solutions to interlocking challenges*"

2. H.E. Mr. Csaba **Korosi**, Director of Environmental Sustainability at the Office of the President of Hungary, was elected to serve as President of the 77th session of the General Assembly on 7 June 2021.

3. PGA-elect **Korosi** has outlined **five priorities for his Presidency**. These are: i) Standing firm on basic principles of the United Nations Charter; ii) Making significant and measurable progress in sustainability transformation; iii) Aiming at integrated, systemic solutions; iv) Enhancing role of science in decision-making; and v) Increasing solidarity to better endure new chapters of crises facing the world.

4. As set out in PGA-elect's priorities, the challenges for the Member States in the coming year will be many. The world continues to grapple with the widespread and still unfolding socio-economic consequences of the **COVID-19 pandemic** and ongoing **geo-political tensions**. PGA-elect has called for **continued reforms** and **strengthening cooperation** among Member States.

5. The Ukraine conflict and its aggravating impact on food security, supply of fuel, and fertilizers on the developing world require collective efforts at the UN to reach creative and affordable solutions. During the 77th UNGA, the UN membership should strive to achieve unity of purpose to find solutions to common challenges of the world.

6. While the world is slowly recovering from the COVID-19 pandemic, this has slowed down the global efforts on the **2030 Agenda** and reversed years of progress on poverty, hunger, health care, education, women empowerment, climate change, access to clean water, and environmental protection. The 'Decade of Action' for the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) needs to be put back on track.

7. **Climate change** is one of the defining challenges of our time. Without drastic collective action, adapting to its impact in the future will be more challenging and costly.

8. The pandemic has also impacted how we fight **terrorism**. The world has witnessed the increased use of terrorism by countries as a means of waging war against others. It is essential for all Member States to not only prevent squandering of gains that have been achieved so far, but also not accept excuses or any justification for terrorism, thereby diminishing the collective fight.

9. These cross-national and cross-domain challenges demand global solidarity and **reformed multilateralism**, based on empowered, functional, and impact-oriented international institutions of governance.

10. The 77th session of the UNGA will also see the continuation of the intergovernmental processes underway as a follow up to the Secretary General's Our Common Agenda Report, which was released as mandated by the UN@75 Political Declaration in September 2021. These processes include a proposed new UN Youth Office, and the Summit of the Future and its various possible thematic tracks, such as a New Agenda for Peace, a Global Digital Compact, and the Declaration for Future Generations. India will continue to play an active role in this process, with an emphasis on a development-centric approach that is Member States' led and owned.

11. Thus, the focus of the 77th UNGA will be on upholding the principles enshrined in the UN Charter, advancing sustainable development goals, overcoming the impact of the pandemic, stimulating development, combating terrorism, strengthening multilateralism, furthering of human rights, combating climate change, and promoting peace and security.

12. India's priorities during 77th UNGA will also be guided by its **core foreign policy objectives**, including supporting and enhancing overall domestic socio-economic growth and strengthening security in its immediate neighborhood, and leading collective global action, in line with the vision of Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi.

13. India is currently serving its **2-year term as a non-permanent Member of the UN Security Council**. During its time on the Council, India has strived to achieve its priorities, i.e., new opportunities for progress; an effective response to international terrorism; reforming the multilateral system; a comprehensive approach to international peace and security; and promoting technology with a human touch as a driver of solutions, by adopting an approach guided by the "Five S's", as set out by the Prime Minister: *Samman* (Respect); *Samvad* (Dialogue), *Sahyog* (Cooperation), and *Shanti* (Peace), to create conditions for universal *Samridhi* (Prosperity). India's overall objective during this tenure in the UN Security Council will be the achievement of N.O.R.M.S: a New Orientation for a Reformed Multilateral System. The 'Five S's will also be the guiding light in our approach to the 77th UNGA. India would also continue to strive to build on our achievements during our August 2021 Presidency of the Security Council, including the focus that was brought on international maritime security by Prime Minister Modi's chairing of the UNSC and adoption of the first PRST on this topic by the Council; a discussion on technology and peacekeeping in the Council chaired by External Affairs Minister, and the adoption of a UNSC Resolution on "Protecting the Protectors" that was co-sponsored by all 15-Member States; and India's contribution of US\$ 1.6 million to UN to develop a situational awareness software platform, "UNITE AWARE" for assisting UN Peacekeeping Missions.

14. At the 77th UNGA, India will also engage on a wide range of issues ranging from political, socio-economic and cultural issues, terrorism, peacekeeping, human rights, legal matters, to

budgetary issues. India shall continue to project its longstanding and growing credentials as a leading South-South development partner, especially in the context of the India-UN Development Partnership Fund, Financing for Development and its leadership on climate change, including through the Lifestyle for Environment (LiFE) movement, the International Solar Alliance (ISA) and Coalition for Disaster Resilient Infrastructure (CDRI)]. India's approach and priorities in the 77th UNGA will also complement its initiatives as President of the G20 for 2023.

B. List of priority areas in 77th UNGA

15. An indicative list of priority issues for India during 77th UNGA are:

1. Maintain India's active engagement as a leading voice on issues relating to **sustainable development, financing for development, terrorism, and climate change**.

2. Strengthen engagement with fellow developing countries, especially LLDCs, LDCs and SIDS through the India-UN Development Partnership Fund and IBSA Fund in the spirit of **South-South cooperation**.

3. Bring India's perspective to debates relating to **human rights** including the right to development and continue to highlight India's achievements in realizing the rights of different groups, including women, children, minorities, and persons with disabilities.

4. Continue to showcase commitments and achievements in women-led development particularly women's leadership and political participation at the grassroots level, promoting financial inclusion, prevention of sexual harassment and violence against women, providing access to clean cooking fuel, sanitation, safe drinking water and health coverage including maternal and child health etc.

5. Continue to advocate the need for **resilient global supply chains** to sustain vaccine production to ensure equitably and affordable access. Promote Indian positions and arguments in consultations and subsequent inter-governmental negotiations on Universal Health Coverage.

6. Attach greater prominence to issues relating to **counter-terrorism**; pushing for more transparency in the process of listing and delisting of entities and individuals in Security Council's Sanction Committees.

7. Engage substantively in matters relating to peacekeeping as a major Troop Contributing Country in finalizing of mandates for **UN peacekeeping missions**. Promote application of technology in peacekeeping Missions and seek accountability for crimes against Peacekeepers in line with Security Council Resolution 2589.

8. Take forward India's pragmatic and constructive approach on **disarmament** issues at the First Committee and UN Disarmament Commission and engage with all partners on issues related to outer space, cyberspace etc.

9. Continue to pursue the issue of **reform of the Security Council** for a meaningful outcome in the 77th UNGA.

10. Continue efforts to further increase the visibility and footprint of the use of **Hindi@UN** project. **Developmental issues and climate action**

16. 2030 Agenda: Strategies for a 'New India' and the country's vision for 2030 are aligned with the spirit of achieving the 2030 Agenda. The various flagship programmes - **Poshan Abhiyaan**,

Ayushman Bharat, Swacch Bharat, Beti Bachao Beti Padhao, Skill India, Ujjwala Yojana, Rural Electrification program, Smart Cities Mission – directly address the challenges highlighted by the SDGs. The slogan of '**Sabka Saath, Sabka Vikas, Sabka Vishwas**' mirrors the essence of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, of leaving no one behind.

17. Localisation of SDGs has been ascribed utmost importance, as the States and Union Territories are the actual implementers of the country's ambitious development agenda. India's success in adopting, implementing, and monitoring SDGs stands testimony to the principle of cooperative federalism. While NITI Aayog sets the high-level framework and monitors progress at national and sub-national levels, the implementation of the SDG agenda is rigorously pursued at the district and block level. A special side-session highlighting the "**Indian Model of SDG Localisation**" during 2022 HLPF was a huge success. India stands ready to share best practices and experiences with partner countries as we reach halfway mark towards the 2030 Agenda.

18. South-South Cooperation: India has considerable experience in South-South Cooperation, bilaterally as well as through collaboration with the UN. India has set up a US\$ 150 million **India-UN Development Partnership Fund**, managed by UNOSSC. The Fund continues to support South-owned and South-led sustainable development projects with a focus on LDCs, LLDCs and SIDS. In four years, the Fund has accumulated a portfolio of 66 projects in 52 countries. As part of **Covid response**, the India-UNDP Fund has commissioned **projects in 15 countries** ranging from Antigua & Barbuda in the Caribbean to Palau in the South Pacific. The IBSA (India-Brazil-South Africa) Fund for the Alleviation of Poverty and Hunger also hosted at the UNOSSC is another unique mechanism for South-South Cooperation. India will also be an active participant in the **5th UN Conference on LDCs** to be held in Doha, Qatar in March 2023. We will continue our commitment in building on our development partnerships.

19. Financing for Development: The *Addis Ababa Action Agenda* aligns domestic & international resource flows, policies, and international agreements with economic, social and environmental priorities. The annual ECOSOC Forum on Financing for Development (FfD Forum) is an intergovernmental process mandated to discuss the follow-up and review of the financing for development outcomes and the means of implementation of the 2030 Agenda. We will continue to contribute to this effort.

20. Eradication of Poverty: One of the long-term effects of the pandemic and ongoing conflicts will be that millions of people will be pushed into extreme poverty. In India, we are implementing a comprehensive development strategy to end poverty in all its forms, through accelerated economic growth and broader social safety nets. We will continue to focus on poverty eradication at the 77th session and share our experience in reducing poverty.

21. Focus on Climate and Water: The 77th session is associated with multiple conferences and meetings — such as **COP27** on climate change in November 2022 that will bring parties together to accelerate action towards the goals of the Paris Agreement and the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change; the **UN Water Conference** in March 2023 that aims to take concerted action to achieve the internationally agreed water-related goals and targets; the **UN Biodiversity Conference** (COP15-second part) in December 2022 that will see the adoption of the post-2020 global biodiversity framework, providing a strategic vision and roadmap for the conservation, protection, restoration and sustainable management of biodiversity for the next decade. India's involvement and voice in these forums will indicate our strong momentum in actively responding to the needs of our planet.

22. India is a leader in Climate Action. Addressing the challenge of climate change requires us to evolve a comprehensive approach which covers education to values, and lifestyle to developmental philosophy. The Prime Minister of India H.E. Mr. Narendra Modi has raised this at

various forums, including at COP 26 in Glasgow, where he highlighted the importance of individual behavior change for catalyzing climate action as part of a **Lifestyle for Environment (LiFE)** Movement. LiFE was launched on World Environment Day 2022. It envisions making individual behavior change the center of the climate action narrative and sustainable lifestyles a global mass movement, thus inviting measurable and scalable behavior change solutions to drive climate-friendly actions amongst individuals and communities.

23. India is one of the few countries that have delivered on its climate action commitments and increasing use of renewable energy going forward. India is also making all efforts towards collective action and building partnerships in the spirit of SDG17 to strengthen climate action. Some of these global initiatives include the **International Solar Alliance**, the **Leadership Group on Industry Transition** and the **Coalition for Disaster Resilient Infrastructure**. We remain committed to continuing the path of ambitious climate action to achieve greener transition for achieving Agenda 2030.

24. As we go into COP 27 this year, there are several threads that need to be addressed: Climate Ambition needs to go hand-in-hand with the **framework for financial, technical, and capacity building support** to countries that need it. It is equally important for countries to fulfill their pre-2020 commitments. The developed countries with their historical experiences, must take lead in the **global transition towards net-zero**. A global Net-Zero should be based on the principle of **common but differentiated responsibility and of equity**, where developing countries will be peaking later given their respective sustainable development paths. Consequently, in order to vacate the carbon space in 2050 for developing countries to grow, the developed countries should, in fact be Net-Minus.

25. India along with South Africa has taken the lead in the WTO on a **COVID-19 vaccine Intellectual Property Rights waiver** and the use of flexibilities of the TRIPS Agreement and the Doha Declaration on TRIPS Agreement and Public Health. We are working actively with GAVI, WHO and ACT Accelerator. India will continue to mobilize Member States towards ensuring equitable and affordable access to COVID-19 vaccines.

26. India's approach to the Education Transforming Education Summit (TES) scheduled on Monday 19 September 2022, would be in line with the National Education Policy, which adopts innovative methods to meet the needs of the 21st century.

D. Human Rights and Social Issues

27. In the coming year, high-level UNGA meetings on appraisal of the **Political Declaration on Universal Health Coverage** (September 2023) and **on Tuberculosis** will be convened.

28. During the 77th session of the General Assembly, India would continue to play a constructive and balancing role on all women-related matters considering India's emphasis on **women-led development** and protection and promotion of women's rights and their central role in implementation of SDGs. India will continue its close cooperation with developing countries, including in the framework of G77 and NAM on social development issues.

29. India will continue to emphasize that discussions on Human Rights at the UN should be held with a constructive approach and the human rights processes at the UN should emphasize on dialogue, cooperation, transparency and non-selectivity in the promotion and protection of all human rights and fundamental freedoms for everyone. The focus of the Human Rights Council, the Office of High Commissioner for Human Rights, and Special Rapporteurs and the entire Treaty Body mechanisms must be to strengthen the capabilities of national governments in their efforts towards promotion and protection of human rights. India has presented three Universal Periodic Reviews on its implementation of various human rights conventions.

30. Under the plenary agenda item '**Culture of Peace**', India will call upon the **United Nations Alliance of Civilizations** for greater inclusivity in the dialogue process to ensure that the inter-religious dialogue is broad-based and encompasses all faiths and is not selective. India would continue to impress that the Alliance should not be used as a platform for divisive political rhetoric and must focus on issues that unite us.

31. **Commission for Social Development**, a functional commission of ECOSOC, is the advisory body responsible for the social development pillar of global development. It is the key United Nations body in charge of the follow up and implementation of the Copenhagen Declaration and Programme of Action adopted at the World Summit for Social Development in Copenhagen in 1995. The sixty-first session of the Commission will take place in February 2022 on the priority theme "Creating full and productive employment and decent work for all as a way of overcoming inequalities to accelerate the recovery from the COVID-19 pandemic and the full implementation of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development". India will continue to use the general debate and other platforms to highlight its national policies and programs focused on inclusive growth, in line with SDGs, and directed towards realization of Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi's vision of '*Atmanirbhar Bharat*' [Self-reliant India].

32. India is a member of the **Commission on the Status of Women**, a functional commission of the UN ECOSOC, the principal global intergovernmental body exclusively dedicated to the promotion of gender equality and the empowerment of women. The Commission takes a leading role in monitoring and reviewing progress and problems in the implementation of the Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action, and in mainstreaming a gender perspective in UN activities. The sixty-seventh session of the Commission will take place in March 2023 on the priority theme "Innovation and technological change, and education in the digital age for achieving gender equality and the empowerment of all women and girls". Given India's leadership role in deployment of technology for efficient public services, the focus will be to share best practices and advocate greater role for women in innovation and technological changes, including digital learning. India will continue to play an active role in negotiating concise and forward-looking sets of recommendations for gender equality and women empowerment globally.

33. India is a member of the **Commission on Population and Development**, a functional commission of ECOSOC, which plays primary role in the follow-up to the implementation of the Programme of Action of the International Conference on Population and Development (ICPD) by reviewing and assessing the implementation of the Programme of Action at the national, regional, and international levels. The fifty-sixth session of the Commission will take place in April 2023 on the theme "Population, Education and Sustainable Development". India will continue to support the working of the Commission interlinking diverse aspects of population, development and human rights in line with the commitment made at the ICPD held in Cairo in 1994. The general debate and other meetings will be utilized to highlight the significant progress made by India in the field of population and sustainable development with a particular focus on inclusive development.

34. India is a member of the **Committee on NGOs** of the ECOSOC which is the inter-governmental body responsible for granting consultative status with ECOSOC to non-governmental organizations (NGOs). As of July 2021, 6,610 NGOs enjoy active consultative status with ECOSOC. While supporting the role of civil society in the working of the UN, India will continue to discharge its duty by exercising due diligence in assessing applications with an aim to prevent misuse of the status by dubious NGOs associating with the UN.

E. Decolonization

35. India was the co-sponsor of the landmark 1960 Declaration on the Granting of Independence to Colonial Countries and Peoples, adopted by the General Assembly, which proclaimed the need to unconditionally end colonialism in all its forms and manifestations. In 1962, India was elected as the first chair of the **Decolonization Committee (Committee of 24)** that was established to monitor implementation of the 1960 Declaration and to make recommendations on its application. India continues to be an active member of the Committee.

F. Disarmament and non-proliferation

36. India is steadfast in its commitment to the goal of **universal, non-discriminatory and verifiable nuclear disarmament**. As a responsible nuclear weapon State, India is committed as per its nuclear doctrine, to maintain credible minimum deterrence with the posture of no-first use and non-use against non-nuclear weapon States. Without diminishing the priority we attach to nuclear disarmament, India supports the immediate commencement of negotiations in the CD of a Fissile Material Cut-off Treaty on the basis of CD/1299 and the mandate contained therein, which remains the most suitable basis for negotiations to commence, as reinforced by the outcomes of the GGE on FMCT as well as the High-Level Expert Preparatory Group on FMCT.

37. India attaches very high importance to the **CWC** and supports all efforts to strengthen the Organization for the Prohibition of Chemical Weapons (OPCW) to enable it to fulfill its mandate within the framework of the Convention.

38. India has been consistent in expressing concerns on the **proliferation of weapons of mass destruction** and their delivery systems, which endangers international peace and security. There is also a growing concern in the international community about the possibility of terrorists acquiring weapons of mass destruction. Through its annual Resolution at the UNGA, titled "Measures to prevent terrorists from acquiring weapons of mass destruction", India has been drawing the attention of the world towards these threats and the need to strengthen international cooperation to address them. India will continue pursue this agenda during 77th UNGA.

39. As a developing country and a major space-faring nation, India has vital interests in **space activities and technologies** that contribute to economic and social development. India has a significant space programme and a well-established framework for international cooperation. India is also a party to major international treaties and conventions relating to outer space activities such as the Outer Space Treaty, Rescue Agreement, Liability Convention and the Registration Convention. India believes that Outer Space should remain an ever-expanding frontier of cooperative endeavour rather than conflict. India will continue to contribute constructively to the discussions under the Open-Ended Working Group on Reducing Space Threats through norms, rules and principles of Responsible Behaviours to further promote and develop common understandings during UNGA 77.

40. Cyberspace is facing an increasing number of challenges in the form of threats and its use for criminal and terrorist purposes. Incidents involving the **malicious use of ICTs** by States and non-State actors have increased in scope, scale, severity, and sophistication. While ICT threats manifest differently across regions, their effects are global and pose a significant risk to international security and stability, economic and social development, as well as the safety and well-being of individuals. Recognising the disparity in cyber preparedness among Member States to tackle various cyber threats and the need to enhance their cyber capabilities, India had proposed the development of a "Global Cyber Security Cooperation Portal" (GCSCP), anchored at the United Nations, as a global platform for international cooperation and coordination amongst Member States on security of cyber infrastructure and improving cyber capabilities.

India will pursue the establishment of this portal along with like-minded countries during UNGA 77 under the auspices of the United Nations in the form of Open-Ended Working Group on security in the use of information and communication technologies 2021–2025 and other similar fora.

G. Peacekeeping

41. India is proud of its **long and rich tradition of contribution to UN peacekeeping** operations. India has contributed more than 260,000 troops in 49 Missions over the years, cumulatively the largest from any country. UN peacekeepers today operate in a complex security environment involving armed groups, non-state actors and terrorists. The ever-expanding mandates of peacekeeping missions with limited resources has only added to the challenges and complexities that peacekeepers face on the ground. The strategy of peacekeepers needing to do more with less, is pushing peacekeeping missions a point of crisis. Peacekeeping missions cannot be a long-term response to what are fundamentally political problems.

42. Against this background, India will work with other troop and police contributing countries towards reducing the burden on peacekeepers with responsibilities which ought to primarily lie with the host state or other relevant international organizations.

43. India will seek to **improve host state capabilities**, especially in security institutions, so as to enable host states to discharge their responsibilities towards protection of civilians and safety and security of Peacekeepers. India will seek to guide the responsible introduction of technology in Peacekeeping Missions with a view to provide maximum benefit to Peacekeepers and local populace.

44. Finally, India will continue to advocate authorization of carefully thought-out **mandates** to peacekeepers in close consultation with troop contributing countries.

F. Counter Terrorism

45. India has always been at the forefront of global counter terrorism efforts. In 1996, long before the adoption of Resolution 1373, India took the initiative to pilot the draft Comprehensive Convention on International Terrorism with the objective of providing a comprehensive legal framework to combating terrorism. India has signed and ratified all the major conventions and protocols on terrorism adopted by the UN and is part of all major global initiatives in that regard.

46. The world will witness the 21st anniversary of 9/11 attack days prior to the UNGA 77. The resolution 1373, adopted in the aftermath of 9/11 attack in 2001, and the Counter Terrorism Committee continue to be the important pillars of the global architecture against terrorism. Other UN initiatives, including the Counter-Terrorism Executive Directorate, also play an important part in augmenting capabilities of member States and extending technical and capacity building assistance. The UN sanctions regime has also been an effective tool in the fight against terrorism.

47. In recent years, terrorist groups and lone wolf attackers have significantly enhanced their capabilities by gaining access to new and emerging technologies, including drones, virtual currencies, and encrypted communications. Social media networks have contributed to the radicalization and recruitment of youth. The COVID-19 pandemic has only further aggravated the situation. Today, the world needs reinvigorated efforts to combat terrorism. Recent developments in our neighbourhood have raised the anxiety of countries with respect to weakening of global efforts to fight terror. The threat of terrorism pervades across the globe with

terrorists adopting to the new situations and expanding to new territories. Cross-border terrorism remains a political tool for certain countries with established credentials of harboring terrorists' sanctioned by the Security Council. Nothing can, and should justify terrorism.

48. India has proposed the following eight-point action plan to the international community in the fight against terrorism: (i) Summon the political will: don't justify terrorism, don't glorify terrorists, (ii) No double standards. Terrorists are terrorists; distinctions are made only at our own peril, (iii) Don't place blocks and holds on listing requests without any reason, (iv) Discourage exclusivist thinking and be on guard against new terminologies and false priorities, (v) Enlist and delist objectively, not on political or religious considerations, (vi) Recognize the linkage to organized crime, (vii) Support and strengthen the FATF, and (viii) Provide greater funding to the UN Office of Counter Terrorism.

49. Terrorism is a priority theme of our two-year tenure in the Security Council from 2021-22. Our action in the council envisages strengthening the multilateral response to counter terrorism. Equally important is to ensure that combating terrorism remains at the center of "Our Common Agenda" set out by the Secretary General, and not at its periphery.

50. As Chair of the Counter Terrorism Committee of the Security Council, India is proposing to organize a Special Meeting of the Committee in Mumbai and New Delhi in October 2022 focusing on the increasing threat posed by the misuse of new and emerging technologies. The special meeting will especially focus on three significant areas where emerging technologies are experiencing rapid development, growing use by Member States (including for security and counter-terrorism purposes), and increasing threat of abuse for terrorism purposes, namely (a) the Internet and social media, (b) terrorism financing, and (c) unmanned aerial systems (UAS).

51. India will continue to pursue implementation of the above priorities in the 77th UNGA and work with other like-minded member states to end the stalemate preventing the adoption of a Comprehensive Convention on International Terrorism.

I. UN Reforms

The reforms of the United Nations, particularly the Security Council will continue to be one of the top priorities for India during the 77th UNGA. Towards this end, India will continue to pursue the Intergovernmental Negotiations (IGN) process in a purposeful manner to initiate **text-based negotiations** to be conducted with an overall objective of achieving concrete outcomes in a **fixed time-frame**.
